

Epistatic interactions among co-inherited malaria-protective red blood cell polymorphisms and their effects across the infection-to-mortality spectrum: a systematic review protocol.

Authors

- ^{1,2} George Paasi* georgepaasi8@gmail.com,
¹ Ruth Namazzi namazzi101@gmail.com,
³ Glorias Asiimwe asiimweglorias@gmail.com,
¹ Grace Ndeezi gndeezi@gmail.com,
¹ Joseph Rujumba rujumbaj@gmail.com,
¹ Christine Sekaggya csekaggya@idi.co.ug,
¹ Ezekiel Mupere mupez@yahoo.com,
¹ Ian Guyton Munabi igkmunabi@gmail.com,
¹ Sarah Kiguli skwalube@yahoo.co.uk,
¹ Richard Idro ridro1@gmail.com,
^{2,4} Peter Olupot-Olupot polupotolupot@yahoo.com,

Author Affiliations

1. Makerere University, college of Health sciences, School of medicine, Department of Paediatric and Child Health.
2. Mbale Clinical Research Institute, Clinical trials unit, P.O. Box 1966, Mbale, Uganda.
3. Busitema University Faculty of Health Sciences, Department of Community and Public Health.
4. Busitema University Faculty of Health Sciences Library.

*Corresponding author: Email: georgepaasi8@gmail.com , Telephone +256701776081 Postal Address P.O. Box 1966, Mbale (Uganda).

Amendments

This is the first version of the protocol. No amendments have been made at the time of initial registration. If any substantial amendments are required after registration (e.g., changes to eligibility criteria, outcome measures, or analysis plan), they will be documented clearly with the date, rationale, and description of the change. Updates will be submitted to PROSPERO and reported in the final review manuscript.

Registration

This systematic review protocol has been submitted for registration with the International Prospective Register of Systematic Reviews (PROSPERO).

PROSPERO registration number: *[To be added upon acceptance]*

The review is being registered in accordance with PRISMA-P guidelines and follows the recommended structure for systematic review protocols. The final registration record will be accessible at: <https://www.crd.york.ac.uk/prospero/>

Introduction/Rationale

Malaria accounts for the strongest selective pressure applied on the human genome as so far elucidated [1-3]. To this end, the human genome has evolved under this selective pressure, with additive human genetic effects thought to account for about a third of the inter-individual variation in susceptibility, protection to, and manifestation of malaria attributable to various host factors [1]. Extensive research has demonstrated the protective role of RBC polymorphisms against malaria. Specifically, the sickle cell trait confers the strongest protective effect against malaria, an effect size of >80%[4]. This reduces the severity of *Plasmodium falciparum* infections by impairing parasite replication within RBCs [5]. Similarly, α -thalassemia in the homozygous state confers approximately 40% protective effect [6]. Furthermore, other protective RBC polymorphisms have been observed in high frequencies in malaria endemic populations. For instance, G6PD deficiency, which induces oxidative stress that damages parasitised RBCs, thereby mitigating disease progression and the O blood group, and variants of the gene for *CR1* [7-9]. Likewise, the Dantu blood group, increase RBC membrane rigidity, limiting parasite invasion and cytoadherence, which are key mechanisms in severe complications like cerebral malaria [10, 11]. Furthermore, Duffy antigen receptor for chemokines (DARC) provides resistance against *Plasmodium vivax* by preventing parasite entry into RBCs [12]. Emerging evidence also highlights the roles of ATP2B4, CR1, and glycophorin A/B hybrids in modulating immune responses and parasite-host interactions [2]. While individual RBC polymorphisms have been extensively studied, their combined effects and potential interactions are poorly understood. For example, the synergistic or antagonistic impact of co-inherited polymorphisms, remains unclear [13-15].

In high-transmission African settings, malaria-protective erythrocyte variants commonly co-occur [16]. However, not all co-inheritances are beneficial. In coastal Kenyan and Ugandan cohorts, HbAS alone reduced severe malaria and malaria-related death by $\approx 80\%$, and α^+ -thalassaemia alone by $\approx 30 - 40\%$, yet children carrying both mutations experienced no protection beyond wild-type levels an archetypal case of negative epistasis Williams et al. 2005 [17]. Understanding such interaction patterns is clinically and strategically urgent. SNP-based genetic-risk scores for malaria susceptibility rely on accurate genotype–phenotype modelling [18], genotype-informed analyses of RTS,S vaccine efficacy demonstrate how host alleles shape protection [19], and ecological modelling for mosquito gene-drive interventions depends on precise estimates of allele-frequency dynamics [20]. Clarifying whether co-inherited RBC polymorphisms interact antagonistically, additively or synergistically therefore matters for patient counselling, trial stratification and the discovery of novel therapeutic targets. Yet the evidence base remains fragmented: most primary studies examine a single polymorphism, and existing reviews focus on individual loci such as the role of haemoglobinopathies in malaria resistance [3], the biochemical and immunological mechanisms of sickle-cell trait [21] or protective aspects of G6PD deficiency [22] and diagnostic [23] without synthesising cross-locus interactions. No systematic review has yet collated the epidemiological data on RBC epistasis in human malaria, a gap this study addresses.

Objectives

To characterise the epistatic interactions among co-inherited malaria-protective RBC polymorphisms and determine how these interactions modify malaria risk across the infection-to-mortality continuum in endemic populations.

Methods

Eligibility criteria

Eligibility will be defined using the PICOS framework (Population, Intervention/exposure, Comparator, Outcomes, Study design), supplemented by additional methodological and contextual considerations.

Domain	Inclusion criteria (PICOS)	Exclusions
Population	Humans of any age resident in <i>Plasmodium falciparum</i> endemic areas in Africa or Asia	Traveller cohorts, non-endemic settings, animal or in-vitro experiments
Exposure	Coinheritance of ≥ 2 inherited red-blood-cell polymorphisms with plausible malaria relevance (e.g. HbAS, α^+ -thalassaemia, G6PD A ⁻ , CR1 Sl ₂ /McC ^b , Hp2-1, GSTP1 Ile105Val, CYB5R3 T117S, PIEZO1 E756del, PKLR R41Q)	Single-locus studies; immune-gene or drug-metabolism interactions not involving RBC traits
Comparator	Preferably single-allele carriers; otherwise wild-type homozygotes	Comparisons lacking a suitable single-allele or wild-type reference group
Outcomes	Any of five prespecified endpoints: 1. Parasite density (microscopy/qPCR) 2. Uncomplicated malaria (fever + parasitaemia) 3. Cerebral malaria (Blantyre coma ≤ 2) 4. Severe malaria (WHO criteria) 5. Malaria-attributable mortality	Non-malaria outcomes (e.g. anaemia alone), other <i>Plasmodium</i> species, unvalidated biomarkers
Study design	Prospective or retrospective cohort, case-control or cross-sectional studies reporting genotype-by-outcome data or an interaction term	In-vitro or animal studies, conference abstracts without full methods, reviews/editorials
Other limits	No restriction on language, year or publication status; translations obtained as needed	-

Information sources

To ensure comprehensive retrieval of all eligible studies, both published and unpublished, we will conduct a systematic search of multiple electronic databases, clinical trial registries, preprint platforms, grey literature sources, and reference lists. The bibliographic databases to be searched from inception to 1 June 2025 include MEDLINE via PubMed, EMBASE via Ovid, Web of Science Core Collection, Scopus, African Journals Online (AJOL), CINAHL via EBSCOhost, and PsycINFO via Ovid. These databases were chosen to ensure broad coverage across biomedical, epidemiological, genetic, and public health disciplines relevant to malaria and human polymorphism research.

In addition to peer-reviewed sources, we will search trial registries including ClinicalTrials.gov and the World Health Organization's International Clinical Trials Registry Platform (ICTRP) to identify ongoing or recently completed studies. To capture emerging research and avoid time-lag bias, we will also include preprint repositories such as medRxiv and bioRxiv.

We will extend our search to grey literature sources to minimise publication bias. This will include ProQuest Dissertations and Theses Global, the WHO Institutional Repository for Information Sharing (IRIS), and OpenGrey. Abstract books and proceedings from major tropical medicine conferences such as the American Society of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene (ASTMH) and the European Congress on Tropical Medicine and International Health (ECTMIH) will also be screened. Finally, we will manually screen the reference lists of all included studies (backward citation chasing), perform forward citation tracking in Scopus and Google Scholar, and contact at least ten recognised researchers in the field to identify unpublished data or studies in press. All searches, including date ranges, search strings, and deduplication logs, will be documented and archived via GitHub and Zenodo for full transparency and reproducibility.

Search strategy

The search strategy will be developed in consultation with a professional health sciences librarian and guided by the Peer Review of Electronic Search Strategies (PRESS) 2015 checklist to ensure accuracy, comprehensiveness, and reproducibility. The strategy will combine controlled vocabulary terms (such as MeSH and Emtree) and relevant free-text keywords to capture three core conceptual domains: malaria, red blood cell polymorphisms, and gene-gene

interactions (epistasis). Each search string will be adapted appropriately to the syntax and indexing system of each database.

The malaria concept will include terms such as “*Plasmodium falciparum*,” “malaria,” and “cerebral malaria.” The second concept erythrocyte polymorphisms will incorporate specific variants known to influence malaria susceptibility, including “sickle cell trait,” “HbAS,” “alpha-thalassemia,” “G6PD deficiency,” “complement receptor 1,” “PIEZO1,” “haptoglobin,” and “red blood cell variants.” The third concept will focus on interactions, with terms such as “epistasis,” “coinheritance,” “genetic interaction,” “modifier effect,” “gene-gene interaction,” and “combinatorial genetics.”

The full line-by-line strategies for each database will be made available as a supplementary file. We will use Boolean logic (AND/OR) to combine concept blocks, apply truncation and adjacency operators as appropriate, and use filters to exclude non-human and non-original research. No restrictions will be placed on publication year, language, or geographic setting. Translations will be sought for non-English records where necessary. All retrieved records will be exported into EndNote X9 for reference management. Automated and manual deduplication will be performed before screening. The final search results, exact query strings, and a deduplication log will be uploaded to the project’s GitHub repository and archived on Zenodo for transparency and reproducibility.

Data management

All retrieved records from the database and supplementary source searches will be imported into EndNote X9 reference management software. An initial automated deduplication will be conducted using EndNote’s built-in duplicate identification functions, followed by manual review to ensure the removal of residual duplicates. After de-duplication, the unique references will be exported into Rayyan (Qatar Computing Research Institute), a web-based tool designed to facilitate blinded screening of titles and abstracts by multiple reviewers.

Title and abstract screening will be carried out independently by two reviewers using predefined eligibility criteria. Each reference will be tagged as “include,” “exclude,” or “maybe,” with conflicts resolved through discussion or adjudication by a third reviewer when necessary. The full-text PDFs of all potentially eligible studies will be obtained and imported into Rayyan for the second screening stage, where full texts will be assessed against the inclusion and exclusion criteria. A screening log will be maintained to record reasons for exclusion at the full-text stage.

For studies meeting inclusion criteria, data extraction will be managed using REDCap (Research Electronic Data Capture), a secure, web-based platform hosted at our institution. We will design and pilot a structured data extraction form within REDCap to ensure clarity, consistency, and completeness. Two reviewers will extract data in parallel for each study. The data will include study characteristics, participant demographics, genotype combinations, malaria outcomes, statistical effect estimates, and risk-of-bias features. All extracted data and reviewer decisions will be version-controlled and auditable. Following extraction, the final dataset will be exported from REDCap into R for synthesis and visualisation. The complete audit trail including decisions at each screening stage, extraction forms, and data exports will be deposited in an open-access GitHub repository and archived on Zenodo under a citable DOI to ensure full transparency and reproducibility of the review workflow.

Selection process

The selection process will be conducted in two distinct stages: an initial screening of titles and abstracts, followed by full-text review. All references retrieved from the searches will first be imported into EndNote X9 for deduplication. The deduplicated library will then be uploaded to Rayyan, an online platform designed to facilitate independent, blinded screening by multiple reviewers.

In the first stage, two reviewers will independently screen all titles and abstracts using the predefined inclusion and exclusion criteria outlined in Section 7. Each record will be labelled as “include,” “exclude,” or “unsure.” Discrepancies between reviewers at this stage will be resolved through discussion. If consensus cannot be reached, a third senior reviewer will adjudicate.

Full-text articles will be retrieved for all references marked as “include” or “unsure” during the initial screening. These full texts will be assessed in duplicate against the same eligibility criteria. During this stage, the reviewers will also document explicit reasons for exclusion for any study not meeting the inclusion criteria. Reasons for exclusion will be coded and summarised in the PRISMA 2020 flow diagram, which will accompany the final report.

To ensure reliability, inter-reviewer agreement will be measured at both stages using Cohen’s kappa statistic. Training and calibration exercises will be conducted prior to screening to improve consistency between reviewers. All decisions made during the selection process, including exclusions at the full-text stage and justifications, will be recorded in a structured log.

This log will be made publicly available in the GitHub repository alongside the final dataset to promote transparency and allow for external auditing of selection decisions.

Data extraction items

Data extraction for this review will be conducted using a structured form developed and piloted in REDCap (Research Electronic Data Capture), a secure, web-based platform hosted by our institution. The form will be informed by the PICOS framework and tailored to the specific exposures and outcomes of interest in this review. Two reviewers will independently extract data from each eligible study, working in parallel to minimise transcription errors and bias. Any discrepancies in extracted data will be resolved through discussion, with arbitration by a third reviewer if consensus cannot be reached.

From each included study, we will extract bibliographic details including first author, year of publication, country and setting, and study design (e.g. case-control, cohort, or cross-sectional). Information on participant characteristics will also be recorded, including sample size, age distribution, sex composition, and malaria transmission intensity of the study location.

For exposures, we will extract full details on the red blood cell polymorphisms evaluated, the methods used to genotype participants (such as PCR or sequencing), quality control measures (e.g. call rate, Hardy-Weinberg equilibrium), and the specific multilocus genotype combinations compared. The reference group used in the analysis (e.g. wild-type homozygotes or single-variant carriers) will also be noted.

Outcome data will include the definitions used for each malaria endpoint (such as parasite density, uncomplicated malaria, severe malaria by WHO criteria, cerebral malaria, or malaria-related mortality), along with the methods of ascertainment (e.g. microscopy, PCR, clinical records, verbal autopsy). We will extract effect estimates including odds ratios, incidence rate ratios, or mean differences along with 95% confidence intervals, and record whether these estimates were adjusted for confounders. Where available, we will also capture author-reported interaction terms or effect modification analyses, and classify the direction of the interaction as additive, synergistic, antagonistic, or indeterminate.

Additional contextual variables will be extracted, including whether the study stratified analyses by age, sex, G6PD enzymatic activity, or geography. These stratified results will be recorded separately. Lastly, we will document information relevant to risk-of-bias assessment, such as sampling strategy, genotyping accuracy, confounding control, precision of effect estimates,

outcome measurement validity, and completeness of data. All extracted data, including the final dataset, extraction audit trail, and the REDCap template, will be deposited in a publicly accessible GitHub repository and archived on Zenodo to ensure transparency and reproducibility.

Risk of bias assessment

To assess the methodological quality of included studies, we will use an adapted version of the Newcastle-Ottawa Scale (NOS), tailored specifically for genetic epidemiology studies evaluating multilocus interactions. This adaptation preserves the three original NOS domains: Selection, Comparability, and Exposure/Outcome while integrating additional criteria to reflect common sources of bias in studies of epistatic interactions, such as genotyping reliability and sparse dual-carrier strata. Each included study will be assessed independently by two reviewers. For each domain, the reviewers will assign a judgement of “low,” “moderate,” or “high” risk of bias, based on a structured set of signalling questions. Discrepancies between reviewers will be resolved through discussion and, if necessary, consultation with a third reviewer.

The adapted tool will include seven specific domains: (1) case selection and sampling frame; (2) representativeness of the control or comparison group; (3) accuracy and completeness of genotyping (including call rate and assay quality); (4) control for confounding (e.g. adjustment for age, sex, transmission intensity); (5) precision, assessed by sample size and the number of individuals carrying both protective polymorphisms; (6) validity of outcome ascertainment, including the use of standard malaria definitions (such as WHO criteria) and diagnostic tools; and (7) handling of missing data and exclusions. An overall risk-of-bias judgement will be derived for each study based on prespecified rules: studies with two or more domains rated “high” or one “high” plus serious imprecision will be classified as having serious risk of bias; those with one “high” or three or more “moderate” domains will be rated as moderate risk; and all others will be considered low risk. The results of the risk-of-bias assessment will be presented visually using the *robvis* package in R. This will include a traffic-light matrix showing domain-level assessments across all included studies, and a stacked bar chart summarising the distribution of risk-of-bias ratings across domains. These outputs will inform the certainty of evidence ratings under GRADE, particularly for the domains of risk of bias and imprecision. All domain criteria, scoring rules, and reviewer decisions will be archived alongside the extracted data and deposited in the open-access GitHub repository for full transparency and reproducibility.

Data synthesis

The approach to data synthesis will be determined by the number, quality, and homogeneity of eligible studies identified. Where possible, we will undertake a quantitative meta-analysis of epistatic effects between co-inherited red blood cell polymorphisms on malaria-related outcomes. For genotype pairs and outcomes assessed in at least three independent studies with comparable exposure and outcome definitions, we will consider meta-analysing effect estimates (e.g. odds ratios, incidence rate ratios, or geometric mean ratios). Effect estimates will be pooled using random-effects models to account for between-study variability. We will assess heterogeneity using the I^2 statistic and explore its sources through subgroup and sensitivity analyses. Meta-analyses will be conducted in R using the meta and metafor packages. Where statistical pooling is not appropriate due to substantial clinical or methodological heterogeneity, inconsistent comparator definitions, or insufficient data we will adopt a structured narrative synthesis guided by the Synthesis Without Meta-analysis (SWiM) reporting framework. This will involve grouping studies by genotype pair and malaria outcome domain (e.g. parasite density, uncomplicated malaria, severe malaria), and classifying the direction of reported or inferred interaction as additive, synergistic, antagonistic, or indeterminate. Classification rules will be defined a priori and applied consistently across studies. If narrative synthesis is required, results will be displayed using summary tables and visualisations such as heat maps and forest plots to illustrate interaction direction and certainty. All synthesis decisions, including any deviations from the planned meta-analytic strategy, will be transparently documented and justified in the final review report.

Subgroup and sensitivity analyses

If sufficient data are available, we will explore whether the direction or magnitude of epistatic interactions between malaria-protective red blood cell polymorphisms varies across key subgroups. Subgroup analyses will be performed based on prespecified effect modifiers that have biological and epidemiological plausibility to influence gene–gene interactions.

Specifically, we will examine the following subgroup comparisons where reported:

1. Age (e.g. children under 5 years vs. older children or adults), to account for immune maturity and age-specific exposure patterns

2. Sex, particularly for X-linked traits such as G6PD deficiency, which may exert differential effects in males and females
3. Geographic setting, to capture differences in transmission intensity, background allele frequencies, or parasite genetic diversity

Where multiple studies provide stratified results for the same genotype pair and outcome within a subgroup (e.g. sex-specific HbAS + G6PD A⁻ interactions), we will compare effect estimates across strata to identify potential effect modification. These stratified analyses will be presented descriptively or via stratified forest plots. However, we will not perform statistical tests for interaction unless such tests are reported in the primary studies.

For sensitivity analyses, we will assess the robustness of our findings by restricting synthesis to studies at low or moderate risk of bias, as judged by our adapted Newcastle-Ottawa Scale. We will also explore the impact of excluding studies with small dual-carrier strata (e.g. fewer than 30 participants) and those with imprecise outcome definitions. Any changes in direction or strength of observed patterns under these sensitivity conditions will be reported.

All subgroup and sensitivity analyses will be contingent on data availability and methodological comparability across studies and will be clearly described in the final review report.

Assessment of certainty in the body of evidence

The certainty of evidence for each genotype pair-outcome combination will be evaluated using the GRADE (Grading of Recommendations, Assessment, Development and Evaluations) approach, adapted for observational studies of genetic associations. GRADE assessments will be conducted independently by two reviewers, with disagreements resolved by discussion or arbitration by a third reviewer.

Each comparison will be assessed across five GRADE domains: risk of bias, inconsistency, indirectness, imprecision, and publication bias. We will use structured rules to guide downgrading within each domain. Risk of bias will reflect the quality of individual studies contributing to each comparison, based on the adapted Newcastle-Ottawa Scale. Inconsistency will be judged by the degree of agreement in direction and magnitude of effect across studies. Indirectness will be considered present if the study population, exposures, or outcomes do not fully align with the review question. Imprecision will be evaluated by the width of confidence intervals and the number of dual-carriers analysed. Publication bias will be considered if evidence is derived from a small number of studies, all reporting positive associations.

Where evidence is limited to narrative synthesis, GRADE criteria will be applied qualitatively, and judgments will be justified transparently. The starting level for all evidence will be “low” due to the observational nature of the data, with downgrading or upgrading based on the GRADE criteria. Certainty ratings (high, moderate, low, very low) will be summarised in a ‘Summary of Findings’ table for each key outcome and interaction. The full set of GRADE ratings, explanations, and evidence profiles will be provided as supplementary material and made publicly accessible via the review’s GitHub repository.

Plans for dissemination

Findings from this systematic review will be disseminated through multiple academic and public channels to maximise reach and impact. The primary mode of dissemination will be the publication of a peer-reviewed manuscript in an open-access journal specialising in infectious diseases, genetics, or global health. The manuscript will follow PRISMA 2020 guidelines to ensure methodological transparency and reporting completeness.

To facilitate reproducibility and enable reuse by other researchers, all components of the review workflow including search strategies, screening logs, extracted datasets, synthesis scripts, and evidence grading outputs will be made publicly available via a structured GitHub repository and permanently archived in Zenodo with an assigned DOI. This open-access repository will allow other investigators to trace, verify, and build upon the review findings.

In addition, results will be presented at relevant international scientific meetings such as the American Society of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene (ASTMH), the European Congress on Tropical Medicine and International Health (ECTMIH), and the African Society of Human Genetics (AfSHG). We also plan to share tailored briefs with policymakers and stakeholders in malaria-endemic regions to highlight implications for surveillance, genetic screening, and therapeutic research. Where possible, we will coordinate with existing malaria genetic epidemiology consortia and data-sharing initiatives to ensure alignment and avoid duplication. A plain-language summary of findings will be developed for broader public dissemination, especially in settings affected by malaria where red blood cell polymorphisms are common.

Review status and timeline

At the time of protocol registration, this systematic review is in the preparatory phase. The research team has finalised the review question, developed the eligibility criteria, and completed

a draft search strategy in collaboration with an experienced information specialist. No formal screening, data extraction, or synthesis has yet been initiated.

Following registration in PROSPERO, we anticipate launching the database searches immediately. Title and abstract screening is scheduled to begin at the end of July 2025, with full-text retrieval and review to follow. Data extraction and risk of bias assessments will be conducted in parallel during August 2025, using a calibrated form developed in REDCap. Synthesis and GRADE evaluations will take place towards end of August 2025 with manuscript drafting expected in early September 2025. Submission of the final manuscript is targeted for end of September 2025.

Throughout the process, all decisions, revisions, and protocol amendments will be logged and documented on the GitHub repository, which will serve as the living record of the review. If the scope of the project changes or if additional subgroup or sensitivity analyses are introduced, these modifications will be formally reported in both the PROSPERO record and the final publication. This timeline reflects the anticipated pace under current staffing and funding conditions. Any major changes to the workflow or deadlines will be updated promptly to maintain transparency and accountability.

Declaration

Ethics approval and consent to participate

Not applicable. This study is based on previously published data and does not involve direct human participants or access to identifiable personal data. Ethical approval is therefore not required.

Funding

None

Competing interests

The authors declare no known competing interests that could influence the conduct or reporting of this systematic review.

Consent for publication

Not applicable.

Availability of data and materials

All data underlying this review including search strategies, screening logs, extraction forms, synthesis scripts, and GRADE assessments will be deposited in a publicly accessible GitHub repository and archived on Zenodo under a DOI, available upon request or publication.

Authors' contributions

GP conceptualised the study, developed the protocol, and led the drafting of the manuscript. RN, SK, RI, and POO contributed to the refinement of the methodology, critical revision of the protocol, and supervision. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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References

1. López, C., et al., *Mechanisms of genetically-based resistance to malaria*. *Gene*, 2010. **467**(1-2): p. 1-12.
2. Kariuki, S.N. and T.N. Williams, *Human genetics and malaria resistance*. *Human genetics*, 2020. **139**(6-7): p. 801-811.
3. Taylor, S.M., C.M. Parobek, and R.M. Fairhurst, *Haemoglobinopathies and the clinical epidemiology of malaria: a systematic review and meta-analysis*. *The Lancet infectious diseases*, 2012. **12**(6): p. 457-468.
4. Williams, T.N., et al., *Sickle cell trait and the risk of Plasmodium falciparum malaria and other childhood diseases*. *J Infect Dis*, 2005. **192**(1): p. 178-86.
5. Pasvol, G., D.J. Weatherall, and R.J.M. Wilson, *Cellular mechanism for the protective effect of haemoglobin S against P. falciparum malaria*. *Nature*, 1978. **274**(5672): p. 701-703.
6. Ndila, C.M., et al., *Human candidate gene polymorphisms and risk of severe malaria in children in Kilifi, Kenya: a case-control association study*. *Lancet Haematol*, 2018. **5**(8): p. e333-e345.
7. Williams, T.N., *Host genetics*. *Advances in Malaria Research*, 2016: p. 465-494.
8. Opi, D.H., et al., *Two complement receptor one alleles have opposing associations with cerebral malaria and interact with α + thalassaemia*. *Elife*, 2018. **7**: p. e31579.

9. Ahmed, J.S., et al., *Influence of blood group, Glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase and Haemoglobin genotype on Falciparum malaria in children in Vihiga highland of Western Kenya*. BMC Infect Dis, 2020. **20**(1): p. 487.
10. Kariuki, S.N., et al., *The Dantu blood group prevents parasite growth in vivo: evidence from a controlled human malaria infection study*. Elife, 2023. **12**: p. e83874.
11. Kariuki, S.N., et al., *Red blood cell tension protects against severe malaria in the Dantu blood group*. Nature, 2020. **585**(7826): p. 579-583.
12. Miller, L.H., et al., *The resistance factor to Plasmodium vivax in blacks: the Duffy-blood-group genotype, FyFy*. New England Journal of Medicine, 1976. **295**(6): p. 302-304.
13. Atkinson, S.H., et al., *Epistasis between the haptoglobin common variant and α + thalassemia influences risk of severe malaria in Kenyan children*. Blood, The Journal of the American Society of Hematology, 2014. **123**(13): p. 2008-2016.
14. Mmbando, B.P., et al., *Negative epistasis between sickle and foetal haemoglobin suggests a reduction in protection against malaria*. PloS one, 2015. **10**(5): p. e0125929.
15. Williams, T.N., et al., *Negative epistasis between the malaria-protective effects of α + thalassemia and the sickle cell trait*. Nature genetics, 2005. **37**(11): p. 1253-1257.
16. Mwakasungula, S., et al., *Red blood cell indices and prevalence of hemoglobinopathies and glucose 6 phosphate dehydrogenase deficiencies in male Tanzanian residents of Dar es Salaam*. Int J Mol Epidemiol Genet, 2014. **5**(4): p. 185-94.
17. Williams, T.N., et al., *Negative epistasis between the malaria-protective effects of α + thalassemia and the sickle cell trait*. Nat Genet, 2005. **37**(11): p. 1253-7.
18. Tai, K.Y., J. Dhaliwal, and K. Wong, *Risk score prediction model based on single nucleotide polymorphism for predicting malaria: a machine learning approach*. BMC Bioinformatics, 2022. **23**(1): p. 325.
19. Juraska, M., et al., *Genotypic analysis of RTS,S/AS01_E malaria vaccine efficacy against parasite infection as a function of dosage regimen and baseline malaria infection status in children aged 5–17 months in Ghana and Kenya: a longitudinal phase 2b randomised controlled trial*. The Lancet Infectious Diseases, 2024. **24**(9): p. 1025-1036.
20. Mondal, A., V.N. Vásquez, and J.M. Marshall, *Target Product Profiles for Mosquito Gene Drives: Incorporating Insights From Mathematical Models*. Frontiers in Tropical Diseases, 2022. **Volume 3 - 2022**.
21. Gong, L., et al., *Biochemical and immunological mechanisms by which sickle cell trait protects against malaria*. Malaria Journal, 2013. **12**(1): p. 317.
22. Mbanefo, E.C., et al., *Association of glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase deficiency and malaria: a systematic review and meta-analysis*. Scientific Reports, 2017. **7**(1): p. 45963.
23. Ley, B., et al., *Methods for the field evaluation of quantitative G6PD diagnostics: a review*. Malaria Journal, 2017. **16**(1): p. 361.

COMPLETE ELECTRONIC SEARCH STRATEGIES

PubMed / MEDLINE

```
(("Malaria, Falciparum"[Mesh] OR malaria[tiab] OR falciparum[tiab])
AND
(("Genotype"[Mesh] OR genotype*[tiab] OR polymorphism*[tiab] OR
allele*[tiab])
AND
(HbAS[tiab] OR "hemoglobin S"[tiab] OR HbAC[tiab] OR "hemoglobin C"[tiab]
OR "alpha thalassemia"[tiab] OR "α-thalassaemia"[tiab]
OR HBA1[tiab] OR HBA2[tiab]
OR G6PD[tiab] OR "glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase"[tiab]
OR Dantu[tiab] OR "glycophorin AB"[tiab] OR GYPB-A[tiab]
OR PIEZO1[tiab] OR ATP2B4[tiab]
OR haptoglobin[tiab] OR "blood group O"[tiab]))
AND
(epistasis[tiab] OR "gene-gene"[tiab] OR coinherit*[tiab] OR "co-
inherit*" [tiab]
OR interaction*[tiab] OR synerg*[tiab] OR antagonis*[tiab] OR
additive[tiab]))
```

EMBASE (Ovid)

```
1 exp malaria/ or exp plasmodium falciparum/ or malaria.mp.
2 exp genotype/ or exp genetic polymorphism/ or allele*.mp.
3 (HbAS or "hemoglobin S" or HbAC or "hemoglobin C" or "alpha thalassemia"
or "α-thalassaemia" or HBA1 or HBA2 or G6PD or "glucose 6 phosphate
dehydrogenase"
or Dantu or PIEZO1 or ATP2B4 or haptoglobin or "blood group O").mp.
4 (epistasis or "gene gene" or coinherit* or "co inherit*" or interaction*
or synerg* or antagonis* or additive).mp.
5 1 and 2 and 3 and 4
6 limit 5 to human
```

Web of Science (Core Collection)

```
TS=((malaria OR falciparum) AND
(genotype* OR polymorphism* OR allele*) AND
("hemoglobin S" OR HbAS OR HbAC OR "hemoglobin C"
OR "alpha thalassemia" OR "α-thalassaemia"
OR G6PD OR Dantu OR PIEZO1 OR ATP2B4
OR haptoglobin OR "blood group O")
AND
(epistasis OR "gene-gene" OR coinherit* OR "co-inherit*"
OR interaction* OR synerg* OR antagonis* OR additive))
```

Scopus

TITLE-ABS-KEY (malaria OR falciparum)
AND TITLE-ABS-KEY (genotype* OR polymorphism* OR allele*)
AND TITLE-ABS-KEY ("hemoglobin S" OR HbAS OR HbAC OR "hemoglobin C"
OR "alpha thalassemia" OR "α-thalassaemia"
OR G6PD OR Dantu OR PIEZO1 OR ATP2B4
OR haptoglobin OR "blood group O")
AND TITLE-ABS-KEY (epistasis OR "gene-gene" OR coinherit* OR "co-inherit*"
OR interaction* OR synerg* OR antagonis* OR additive)

CINAHL (EBSCOhost)

(MH "Malaria+") AND
(MH "Genotype" OR MH "Polymorphism, Genetic" OR TX genotype* OR TX
polymorphism* OR TX allele*) AND
(TX "hemoglobin S" OR TX HbAS OR TX HbAC OR TX "hemoglobin C"
OR TX "alpha thalassemia" OR TX G6PD OR TX Dantu OR TX PIEZO1
OR TX ATP2B4 OR TX haptoglobin OR TX "blood group O") AND
(TX epistasis OR TX "gene gene" OR TX coinherit* OR TX "co inherit*"
OR TX interaction* OR TX synerg* OR TX antagonis* OR TX additive)
Limiters: Human

PsycINFO (ProQuest)

NOFT(malaria OR falciparum) AND
NOFT(genotype* OR polymorphism* OR allele*) AND
NOFT("hemoglobin S" OR HbAS OR HbAC OR "hemoglobin C"
OR "alpha thalassemia" OR "α-thalassaemia"
OR G6PD OR Dantu OR PIEZO1 OR ATP2B4
OR haptoglobin OR "blood group O") AND
NOFT(epistasis OR "gene gene" OR coinherit* OR "co inherit*"
OR interaction* OR synerg* OR antagonis* OR additive)

Cochrane Library (CENTRAL)

(malaria OR falciparum):ti,ab,kw AND
(genotype* OR polymorphism* OR allele*):ti,ab,kw AND
(("hemoglobin S" OR HbAS OR HbAC OR "hemoglobin C"
OR "alpha thalassemia" OR "α-thalassaemia"
OR G6PD OR Dantu OR PIEZO1 OR ATP2B4
OR haptoglobin OR "blood group O"):ti,ab,kw) AND
(epistasis OR "gene gene" OR coinherit* OR "co-inherit*"
OR interaction* OR synerg* OR antagonis* OR additive):ti,ab,kw

African Journals Online (AJOL)

(malaria OR falciparum) AND
(HbAS OR HbSS OR "alpha thalassemia" OR G6PD OR Dantu) AND
(epistasis OR "gene gene" OR interaction OR synerg OR antagonistic)
Search fields: Title + Abstract + Keywords

pre-print servers (medRxiv & bioRxiv)

All terms: (malaria OR falciparum) AND
(genotype* OR polymorphism* OR allele*) AND
(HbAS OR "alpha thalassemia" OR G6PD OR Dantu OR PIEZO1) AND
(epistasis OR "gene gene" OR coinherit* OR interaction*)
